

The Role I-Pad in Promoting the Students Classroom Engagement

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Abstract

In tertiary education teachers need innovative strategies to communicate with students of the next generation and to shape enticing educational involvements for them. The use of new methods such as video-recorded lectures to communicate directly and individually with all students has been the preserve of tech-savvy educators. A recent technological advance – the Apple iPad – has the possible to change this situation, offering access to effective and efficient pedagogy in an easy and spontaneous way. This paper is a report on the use of the iPad in teaching accomplishments over the past few years, showing how it can be used to develop engagement with learning for tertiary students, both those studying live on campus and those learning at a distance.

Keywords: iPad, Technology in Education, Student Engagement.

Introduction

The term m-learning (or mobile-learning), future development once e-learning, has recently created its approach into the literature on tertiary education. M-learning refers to the benefits afforded by mobile technologies like the most recent generation of mobile telephones and pill computers. Such technologies have the potential to basically modification the ways in which learning and teaching square measure distributed greatly affirmative artist and cooperative approaches to learning, and versatile approaches to teaching. The most recent developments in such technology embrace the iPad, remarked as ‘post-PC devices’ or PPDs by Irish potato (2011) in his discussion of early adoption in tertiary education of iPad technology.

Although the iPad may be a new product (the 1st version was discharged in 2010), it’s already been the topic of studies investigation its use in teaching. Kinash et al. (2011) represented AN Australian investigation to gauge the impact on learning of students’ use of mobile devices like the iPad; feedback from students was positive and optimistic, despite the fact that most students failed to believe that their learning had improved. Hall ANd Smith (2011) represented an iPad initiative in a very North American country graduate management program and noted that whereas learning outcomes weren’t considerably improved, student convenience and

suppleness were increased, at the side of aspects of environmental property. Jalali and colleagues (2011) rumoured on the utilization of an iPad in finishing up a multiple-choice examination in anatomy at a Canadian university; whereas all participants likable the concept and it saved vital paper resources, students rumoured further stress from a probably unreliable web and worries regarding their responses being properly recorded and submitted.

The previous reports square measure supported students learning supported by individual iPads. They ride earlier studies of scholars utilizing pill PCs, like the gathering emended by Reed and Berque Van Oostveen, Muirhead and clarinettist (2011) additionally investigated the experiences of scholars exploitation pill PCs, finding very little proof of significant learning with the technology and no proof of fixing attitudes; however line of work for similar studies cantered on new devices like the iPad. In contrast, Romney (2009) rumoured accumulated retention and performance of arithmetic students’ exploitation pill PCs with synchronic and searchable files containing audio recordings of teacher (and student) comments and annotations captured throughout a mathematical problem-solving session. Earlier, Freake (2008) conferred a positive report on the effectiveness and acceptableness of electronic marking (grading) of physics assignments employing a pill laptop. Comparatively few papers have thought-about the uses that academics will create of a post-PC device like the iPad, and it’s hoped that this paper will fill such a niche in current reports.

This paper may be a report on the extraordinary and continuous use of the iPad in a very vary of teaching activities over the previous fifteen months. The experiences represented, and therefore the edges found, significantly the accumulated engagement of square measure seemingly to be attention-grabbing for different lecturers in a very vary of tertiary courses. It’s a part of our job as tertiary educators to supply our students’ attention-grabbing and relevant learning experiences, and during this endeavour we should always be creating most use of the options of current technology.

Possible uses of the iPad

The iPad has been employed by the primary author within the context of 2 units offered by the Department of Statistics at Macquarie University (Sydney, Australia): a sophomore Introduction to chance unit (PROB) and a masters-level unit Mathematical Background for Biostatistics (BCA), delivered through the Biostatistics pool of Australia (Simpson, 2009). Statistics at Macquarie features a sturdy assortment of offerings in commission teaching and attracts students from various areas, like scientific discipline, social science and therefore the biological sciences. many units have the responsibility to introduce students to the essential ideas of arithmetic and chance. Students usually return from totally different square measures of study and are either ‘internal’ students finding out on field or ‘external’ students finding out in distance mode, young or mature, full- time students or regular staff, taking their degree or even practiced teachers in a very totally different field of analysis. it’s clear that the challenges across each unit and each cluster of scholars vary considerably. the utilization of technology, and especially of the iPad, has expedited a mode of teaching in these 2 units that takes account of the overall wants of the scholars and nevertheless is ready to be aware of their individual requests. The iPad has been used as a way to have interaction, inspire and encourage students through high-level presentation and communication tools. it’s modified the pedagogic approach, creating the educational expertise less complicated and nevertheless deeper. The results show that students learn best once technologies square measure seamlessly integrated into the programme to boost their learning expertise, as highlighted by this comment.

The videos square measure nice. while not the videos would just about be like teaching myself maths through reading textbooks (which makes Maine surprise why anyone would wish to pay to try to to this course!). (BCA student, Discussion Forum message, 2011)

In the following sections, the utilization of the iPad as a tool to speak with students, turns out video lectures and marks assignments are mentioned.

Lectures for Internal Students

Lectures with students attending on field have sometimes followed a standard format – and so this is often prescribed by the Department so as to keep up flexibility in staffing. Sticking out slides and talking regarding the chance content with students WHO might not have an immediate interest in statistics will simply lead to disengagement. though the slides square measure designed to be ‘interesting’, with legion examples from reality and formulae tied integrally to those examples, they’re not enough to have interaction students coming back from totally different areas of interest. Especially, the slides square measure static. to beat this drawback, the amount of explanations and digressions from the slides to the whiteboard are often accumulated, to permit students to check however everything are often engineered from the bottom up. Students’ feedback on this approach is typically positive, however they usually lack expertise in taking adequate notes and therefore the edges of the approach square measure simply lost.

With the adoption of the iPad, the presentation and communication throughout lectures will modification. Rather than static slides, spirited and spontaneous shows are often created. Slides are often annotated on the iPad itself in real time, the utilization of the whiteboard are often laid-off, and each note, graph or formula written throughout the lecture will currently be recorded. The interest and therefore the participation of scholars in lectures exploitation such an approach square measure evidently higher, and therefore the students feel ‘safer’ in this they recognize they’re going to be ready to access the small print later.

Feedback through formal analysis of teaching forms and informal discussion with students has been irresistibly positive. In AN anonymous survey conducted late in 2010 with eighteen PROB students, fourteen declared that the new lecture approach was ‘more useful’, four expressed no preference and no-one expressed a need to travel back to the normal teaching vogue.

Lectures for External Students

The video lectures square measure a happening. Observation them before endeavour the textbook makes the subject abundant less intimidating. Also, observation somebody bear the steps Mainethodically permits me to form the very important connections that the textbook ne’er expressly states. Please keep them coming! (BCA student, Discussion Forum message, 2011)

Distance students square measure in a very fully totally different class from internal students. they’re sometimes older and a lot of mature, and infrequently have a regular job – perhaps in a very applied math space and perhaps in another connected profession. The iPad has been tested in each the units: within the 1st (PROB), the bulk of the scholars square measure internal and therefore the few external students share with them the content and therefore the assessment of the unit. The second unit (BCA) is obtainable exclusively in distance mode and there are not any physical lectures regular.

Distance Students in Units Offered Internally and Outwardly

It is commonplace apply in our Department (and throughout abundant of Macquarie University) for live lectures to be recorded to be used by external students (and for review by internal students). Even once distance students will access such audio recordings, they’re in a way underprivileged, as they will not see the additional work (explanations, graphs, formulae, etc.) made throughout the lecture. The university system is typically wont to record the audio of the lectures, however in some cases it can even record a video stream; specifically, everything that’s projected are often saved in

a very picture at the side of the audio from the lecture. However, the video risk is presently solely on the market in a very little variety of (usually the largest) lecture theatres. The iPad adapts well to the current configuration, because it permits the lecturer to write down directly on the screen so record the entire lecture – visuals further as audio. exploitation the iPad because the supply for recordings throughout the last 2 semesters, students square measure afforded the chance of accessing the lectures not solely personally, however additionally through the later video. In these recordings, the slides, with audio comment by the lecturer, square measure dynamically annotated as notes, graphs and formulae square measure written on the screen of the iPad. Distance students will currently take pleasure in the entire teaching expertise, within the same approach as if they were within the lecture theatre. this is often a revolution for college students WHO don't seem to be snug in finding out completely exploitation books or notes however cannot register as internal students. it's additionally a side of equity between internal and external students once they share constant assessment arrange.

Distance Students in Units Offered Solely Outwardly

The video lectures square measure fantastic. Maths does not return simple to Maine thus having a video lecture to clarify the necessary ideas before I tackle the text book may be a nice facilitates. (BCA student, Discussion Forum message, 2011).

The BCA may be a pool of bio statistical specialists from around Australia, with representatives from universities, government and therefore the pharmaceutical trade, WHO have combined to supply a program of postgraduate courses (Simpson, 2009). All units' square measure delivered by distance-learning strategies and Mathematical Background for Biostatistics is obtainable by the Department of Statistics at Macquarie University within the second semester of the year.

In this unit, the most issues that previous teams of scholars had rumoured were difficulties within the comprehension of the textbook and therefore the thought to receive individual feedback once seeking facilitate, ideally in a very less technical language than the one utilized in the textbook.

The unit is historically supported anawfully smart textbook (Anton, 2009) and therefore the students have access to a spread of on-line resources. In consultation with students it's become clear that the lecturer's responsibility is to administer students' one thing over a study guide – a listing of topics or set of notes to figure through. Within the current semester, each week short (20-40 minutes) video lectures square measure recorded with the iPad to introduce the topics of the week in an enticing and visual approach, and to inquire into specific details of the textbook chapters. For the lecturer, the method is straightforward and intuitive, and doesn't gift the technical challenges that usually discourage instructors from getting ready video lectures for his or her students. We've found a variety of advantages of this approach, per those known by Romney (2009) WHO utilised technique with an earlier technology.

From the students' perspective, the utilization of such videos provides them the chance of observation constant discussion or clarification as repeatedly as they require, sometimes that specialize in specific passages. they will currently receive the full lecture in a very format that's acquainted and prepares them for more study exploitation the textbook. Knowledgeable scientist will browse through a page full of formulae and understand the message and therefore the connectedness of every step. Several students – even practiced postgraduate students – coming back from different fields of interest will solely see the formulae. For such a student it's going to be an awfully tough job to be told a brand new mathematical language and use it to know new ideas. If, on high of this, additionally has got to overcome the obstacle of being alone within the learning expertise, a standard outcome could also be the withdrawal from the unit. within the 2010cohort, virtually half the scholars (15 of 36) did so withdraw from this unit of study, and this has been

traditionally a typical withdrawal rate. This year, with the introduction of the video lectures, the proportion of withdrawals has declined considerably (4 of 37).

This comment summarizes however the perceptions of external students will modification and what the results are:

Love the video lectures! this is often my third try at finding out statistics via distance ED, and therefore the solely time i have not felt flooded by it all and withdrawn. Recordings of lectures delivered on field {are|ar|areaunit|square Maineasure} usually not useful for external students and have left me feeling lost and disconnected from my studies. These short videos keep my attention and that i have had several “ah ha” moments observation them. I would like all external units can be a bit like this! Thanks. (BCA student, Discussion Forum message, 2011)

The Ipad Won't to Answer Queries

An important moment within the learning expertise is once a student doesn't perceive a subject, a step proof or an exercise. The quality thanks to facilitate him or her is to travel through the question exploitation written words. With the introduction of the iPad into the teaching routine, written answers are often restricted to cases once they square measure applicable and a solution to a student's question are often made within the kind of a mini video lecture specific to the subject or exercise. The educational expertise of distance students is currently fully modified. If they cannot solve a tangle by themselves, there's a brand new possibility: a fanatical video that shows each step of the matter. The format is especially necessary. Written solutions square measure formally constant because the textbook and square measure usually unable to supply with a brand new prospective on the matter. It's common that a lecturer's 1st response to a matter isn't enough and students evoke a lot of insights. A video is different: it permits each step of in a very a lot of natural verbal approach and queries requesting more explanation once such a mini video lecture square measure uncommon. The comments below show clearly the students' purpose of read on this.

Thanks for the shows on question seven and eight they were fantastic and an excellent facilitate. It was interactive and that i might see what you were doing as you were talking Maine through the diagram. Once more thanks for the assistance.

I think that as distance students, this technique of conveyance you to North American country, thus to talk, makes learning tough ideas abundant easier. an excellent example of this was the video you announce in response to forum questions on inequalities. It permits North American country and you to be interactive in our learning. (BCA student, Discussion Forum message, 2011)

Assignment Marking (Grading)

When students complete an assignment, they need a couple of requests that square measure of major importance for his or her learning expertise which are often a lot of simply happy with the utilization of technology. Our approaches are often seen to increase the work of Freake (2008) by utilizing the accumulated options of the most recent generation of technology.

Firstly, students want timely feedback, as a result of they require understanding quickly if the standard or the amount of their study isn't applicable. Within the second place, students ought to recognize what errors they created and in what ways in which their entire assignment might are improved. So as to deal with the primary issue, our expertise is that the utilization of the iPad permits lecturers to own a awfully fast, economical and property work flow in their marking of student work. Students' square measure asked to submit their papers electronically, sometimes in .pdf format, and therefore the lecturer doesn't thought to print them. This fits nicely within the culture that the scholars inhabit, wherever progressively property is seen as a valuable principle. Future step is solely to open the papers in one in all the many apps on the iPad that enable annotation

pdf files. These apps allow the teacher to write, attach notes, typeset, insert stamps or pictures, and even record audio clips onto the students’ papers. Finally, the marked assignments are often come to the coed by email directly from the app used. This marking system has obvious advantages: it’s property, as all the marking is finished electronically, and therefore the teacher will simply maintain AN electronic archive of all the assignments marked while not the necessity to scan them. It can even be simply extended to a cooperative marking system. If the files square measure hosted on a shared networked drive, a team of markers will access and mark the assignments from their computers or tablets where they’re. They don’t want to be within the same work to share the assignment in paper format.

Finally, the solutions to the assignments square measure sometimes distributed within the same type because the papers made by the scholars. This shows the scholars however their final assignment ought to have looked, however not the way to make the results. The steps are often there, however if students square measure unable to administer an accurate answer within the 1st place there’s the chance that they’re going to not absolutely perceive the event of the model answer. However, these learning demands are often happy with the utilization of a video lecture within which the teacher solves the assignment, enriching each step with comments and relevance the textbook or the notes.

Summary and Conclusions

Technology has already modified the educational expertise of scholars in tertiary education many times throughout the last generation. The introduction of the non-public laptop gave instructors and students new ways in which to compose documents, to hold out mathematical tasks and to keep up databases. The switch from the sheet to transparencies to video-projected slides modified the format of lectures and therefore the expectations of scholars registered in tertiary courses. The introduction of e-learning systems gave students, particularly distance students, a virtual place wherever they may access material and participate in discussion forums.

A decade ago, Prensky (2001) noted that the scholars of the day weren’t those that the academic system was designed. With the increasing pace of technological development, that statement is even a lot of true nowadays. up to date ‘digital age’ university students in developed countries square measure acquainted with social networking through Facebook, instant communication via Twitter and mobile technology through their smartphones. They compare these with university e-mail and e-learning systems, projected lecture slides and written assessment tasks. They need expressed a need for a lot of varied sorts of communication and a lot of vivacious learning strategies (Oblinger & Oblinger, 2005).

Even considering aspects not in real time connected to the educational expertise, like property, universities struggle in catching up with the planet and therefore the culture within which the scholars live. they need to alter the new generation of scholars and their new ways in which of learning, giving constant content in new formats. Cultural modification of academics is required, and this is often tough once the technology level needed to evolve is simply too high. To facilitate such modification, academics want a brand new generation of devices and package, simple to use and while not a steep learning curve: the new category of post-PC devices like the iPad can be simply what’s required.

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